

IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE IN TERMS OF TYPE OF AREA AND TYPE OF ADMINISTRATION ON TEACHING COMPETENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

The present study aims to see the the impact of organizational climate in terms of area and type of administration (Govt. & Private) on teaching competence. A sample of 496 secondary school teachers was selected from Jammu district of J&K. Collected data when analyzed revealed that there was significant impact of organizational climate on teaching competence among the school teachers.

Keywords: *Organizational climate, Teaching competence, type of area, type of administration.*

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Introduction

In any organization climate of organization plays a crucial role in achieving the aims and objectives. Since Education is also an important organization, work environment or climate is also one of the crucial factors in this field. Organizational climate is basically perception of a individual about the working conditions of that organizations. There are organizations where due importance is given to facilities like salary, incentives, involvement in decision making, cooperation from head of organization etc. Such a work climate where there is complete freedom, good interpersonal relationship and cooperation is observed is termed as open organizational climate. On the other hand there are organizations where a very strict and controlled behavior is observed on the part of head and no importance is given to the workers ideas. Workers are treated like paid slaves and the only objective is to get maximum productivity. No importance is given to the facilities like salary, incentives, leave etc. The climate of such organizations is termed as closed organizational climate.

Studies revealed that open climate increases the work performance whereas closed climate reduces the work efficiency as results in less output or productivity.

In the field of Education work efficiency can be termed as teaching competency. Teachers are the maker of nation. If we want to develop our nation we must have competent teachers. A competent teacher is one who can realize the aims and objectives of Education. The teacher who is master of his subject, has the knowledge of all the necessary skills, techniques and methods of teaching and the one who can inculcate best among his students is known as competent teacher.

Research studies also advocates an impact of organizational climate on teaching competence among workers in educational system as well as in other organizations. A negative relationship between organizational climate and competence among teachers of secondary schools can be seen, however a significant impact of organizational climate on competency among teachers can be observed (Devi & Mali, 2017). Jena (2012) advocated positive and significant relationship between competence and organizational climate of Madhymik school teachers. Recently Kaur (2017) advocated a significant connection between organizational climate of secondary school teachers and their teaching competence. Babu & Kumari (2013) found difference in effectiveness of teaching in relation to organizational climate to be significant.

Review of Literature

Jena (2012) conducted a study to find relationship between teaching competency and organizational climate. 100 teachers comprising of half male and half female teachers were selected for study. Teaching aptitude battery by Singh & Sharma (2005), teaching competency scale by Passi & Lalitha(1994) and a scale developed by Chaudhari and Pethe (2001) were the tool used. The findings suggested that there is positive relationship and significant difference in teaching competence and organizational climate.

Babu & Kumari (2013) studied organizational climate as predictor of teaching effectiveness. 100 elementary school teachers were selected for study. It was assessed that the difference in teaching effectiveness in relation to organizational climate is significant.

Selamat et al(2013) investigated influence of organizational climate on teachers job performance using a sample of 37 secondary school teachers in. A questionnaire developed by Raza (2010) comprising of three sections for assessing demographic information, organizational climate and teachers job performance was used. The study suggested that school climate was significant factor that influences job performance.

Devi & Mali (2017) studied organizational climate in relation to teaching competency of teachers of Himachal Pradesh. Scale developed by B.K Passi & Ms. Lalitha was used to assess the level of teaching competency and another scale developed by Vanita Singh was used to assess organizational climate. The sample comprises of 600 teachers. It was assessed that there is a significant effect of organizational climate was observed on teaching competency.

Kaur (2017) studied the effect of teaching attitude and organizational climate on teaching competence. 400 secondary school teachers of Punjab state were selected as sample. Teaching attitude scale developed by Kulsum (2008) and organizational climate scale by Pethe, Chaudhari and Dhar (2001) were the tool used. A self developed and standardized scale by the investigator was also used to measure teaching competence. The results of study revealed that organizational climate has significant impact on professional competence of teachers.

Pratami, Harapan & Arafat (2018) conducted a study to see the influence of organizational climate on the performance of junior high school teachers in Bukit Kecil sub district Palembang. Ex facto method was employed for conducting research. The sample of 64 teachers selected from a population of 176 teachers. The results revealed that organizational climate has an influence on job performance of teachers.

Gemnafle et al (2018) studied organizational climate of the school and performance of teachers and found that positive job performance is associated with organizational climate.

Thus it can be said that in any institution where the work environment is conducive the teacher's performance increases. An institution away from closed climate helps to develop healthy competition between the teachers and as a result effectiveness or competency among them likely to increase.

Based on above discussion the investigator of this study has been provoked to study the impact of organizational climate on competence of teachers.

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to assess the significance of impact of Organizational climate in terms of type of area and type of administration on Teaching Competence of secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis

There exist no significant main and joint interaction between Organizational Climate in terms of type of area and type of administration with Teaching Competence as dependent variable of secondary school teachers.

Methodology

Sample

A sample of 496 secondary school teachers working in Jammu district of J&k was selected for the study.

Tool used

Organizational climate scale by Sanjyot Pethe, Sushama Chaudhari and Upinder Dhar.and General teaching competency scale by B.K. Passi and Mrs. M.S. Lalitha. were the tool used

Sample

A sample of 496 secondary school teachers was selected from Jammu district of J&K. The obtained data was classified in terms of good and poor organizational climate using mean and standard deviation and finally a sample of 496 was used for analysis

Analysis

Mean, S.D and ANOVA was used to analyze the data obtained.

Testing of null Hypothesis for significance of interaction between organizational climate in terms of area and type of administration with Teaching Competence as dependent variable

Table no. 1 : Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Type of Area	0	Rural	267
	1	Urban	229
Type of Administration	0	Private	257
	1	Govt.	239
Organizational Climate	1	Poor	286
	2	Good	210

Table no.1 shows the data in terms of good organizational and poor organizational climate. The data for the present study was collected from both rural as well as urban area. Also during collection of data due importance was given to the type of administration (Government or Private schools). Here in above table 0 represents rural area, private administration whereas 1 represents urban area and government administered school. Similarly for organizational climate 1 and 2 represents poor and good organizational climate respectively.

Table No. 2: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects Dependent Variable: Competence.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	16578.292 ^a	7	2368.327	58.009	.000
Intercept	4773679.593	1	4773679.593	1.169E5	.000
Type of Area	152.249	1	152.249	3.729	.054
Type of Administration	.193	1	.193	.005	.945
Organizational climate	14449.211	1	14449.211	353.917	.000
Type of Area * Type of Administration.	242.446	1	242.446	5.938	.015
Type of Area * Organizational climate.	912.691	1	912.691	22.355	.000
Type of Administration * Organizational climate.	155.699	1	155.699	3.814	.051
Type of Area *Type of Administration * Organizational climate	555.723	1	555.723	13.612	.000
Error	19923.377	488	40.827		
Total	5003304.000	496			
Corrected Total	36501.669	495			

a. R Squared = .454 (Adjusted R Squared = .446)

Reporting. A three-way analysis of variance was conducted to test the influence of three independent variables (Area, Type of administration, and organizational climate) on the teaching competence scores of teachers in different secondary schools of Jammu district of Jammu and Kashmir.

Area type include two levels (rural, urban), type of administration included (govt., private) and organization climate included (poor and good).One main effect organizational climate, Two, two factor interaction(except type of administration and organizational climate) and three factor interactions were statistically significant at the .05 significance level except for the main effects type of area and type of administration.

The main effect organization climate yielded an F ratio of $F(1, 496) = 353.917$, $p < .001$, indicating a significant difference between poor organizational climate ($< = 99$) & good organizational climate($> = 122$).

The Two factor interactions, area and type of administration $F(1, 496) = 5.938, p < 0.05$, area and organizational climate $F(1, 496) = 22.355, p < 0.001$ significantly effects the teaching competence scores of teachers.

Finally, the three factor interaction area, type of administration and organizational climate $F(1, 496) = 13.612, p < 0.001$ jointly effects the teaching competence status of the teachers.

This finding is in favour of the results obtained by Selamat et al (2013), Devi & Mali (2017), Kaur (2017), & Pratami, Harapan & Arafat (2018).

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Cite Your Article as:

Rakesh Kumar. (2023). IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE IN TERMS OF TYPE OF AREA AND TYPE OF ADMINISTRATION ON TEACHING COMPETENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182537>